

REMEDYING A FORM IMPROVING A PATIENT/CLINIC NARRATIVE

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ABSTRACT

Forms are a necessary, though often frustrating and tedious part of the contemporary world. In the healthcare narrative, one must begin to acknowledge that many of these forms are frequently designed to address the needs of the healthcare provider, and not necessarily that of the patient, though both ostensibly have the same goal: patient health. In this study, issues in a university student health immunization form are brought to light through a qualitative analysis of its look, content and task structure. This paper examines a redesign with the user in mind, and shows in quantitative and qualitative terms the improvements made, and through a reiterative design process that ultimately eliminated the form.

Keywords: Form Design; Information Design; Qualitative Methods.

INTRODUCTION

As forms are created, it can be easy to fall into a sort of ‘tunnel vision’ in which the creator may focus so narrowly upon their own goals for the form that they may fail to remember the users perceptions and needs. Terminology may be clear to the creator, but not to the intended user for example. This could be seen a type of “professional vision...which consists of socially organized ways of seeing and understanding events that are answerable to the distinctive interests of a particular social group.” (Goodwin, 2001, p. 281). These ways of

seeing are essential for members of groups to communicate to each other, however they can create barriers in communication between dissimilar groups. For example, in the medical field, there are many terms and acronyms that are well understood within that group, however, a patient may not necessarily understand all the terms used in regards to their own care. For example, the two approved meningococcal vaccines in the U.S., MPSV4 and MCV4, may also be referred to as menomune and menactra respectively. Measles, mumps, and rubella may be referred to as MMR. Rubeola may sound like rubella, yet means measles. In many cases, diseases have both a common name and scientific name, such as chickenpox, which is caused by the varicella virus, potentially furthering the confusion.

Filling out forms can be a confusing, tedious, and frustrating process, regardless of the circumstances. Yet they are a frequent and necessary part of modern life, whether they are being utilized in the working world or our personal lives, such as for taxes, drivers license applications, insurance, or for medical care. The intention of this paper is to better understand the component parts of form design within the healthcare environment, and to understand the procedural context of their design.

THE HEALTHCARE NARRATIVE

In a higher education setting and within a student health center, where part of the mission is to not only provide for student health, but also to educate, it would seem to make sense to try and engage students in making decisions in their own care, rather than dictate. These initial experiences with the health care experience could have a long-term influence on a person's view of health and health care providers, and should be a positive and enabling experience.

The impact and impressions of our experiences can have a lasting effect as we gather new information based on novel encounters, and in this way we develop stories that embody this knowledge. "Much of the social information we acquire in daily life is transmitted to us in the form of a narrative. That is, it is conveyed in a thematically and temporally related sequence." (Adaval & Wyer, 1998).

In this particular narrative, a patient's role in healthcare is essentially to be sick, they are often not engaged in their own care, in part because they are indeed ill, but also because the entire experience can be overwhelming. Patients rely upon the experts to aid them in areas where they perhaps have little understanding. This is true in matters of law, in real estate, and for medical decisions. However, an inadvertent and unspoken message could be communicated as well. These necessary and perfectly logical administrative tasks could be interpreted as methods of power and control (Frascara, 2000).

CONDITIONS

The major role of this particular form has been the documentation of various required immunizations, such as measles, and to educate new students on the meningitis virus and meningococcal vaccines. It also serves to remind incoming international students that they are required to be screened for tuberculosis (TB), and to record recommended immunizations for all students. As outlined in a prior paper by this Author (2007), the Immunization Requirement form is one of three forms incoming students must fill out, the others being a Health History form, and an Insurance Form. If an incoming student does not comply with the requirements, or does not complete the forms, they will not be allowed to register for the second semester of their initial year at the university. Approximately ¼ of the original Immunization Requirement forms were incomplete or not filled out at all (Bruski, 2007). This results in additional work for the staff in the health center and potential anxiety for students as they adjust to their first semester of college life, only to find out that their health care center is not allowing them to continue their studies, essentially placing the center in the role of an enforcer. Though the requirement itself is understandable, to place a health center that hopefully provides a trusted service to students in a potentially adversarial role, is less than ideal. New college students are potentially encountering health care services on their own for the first time, and a negative experience could leave a lasting impression.

Additionally, timing for a potential redesign for this particular form was critical as student campus orientations were to take place in a matter of weeks, and these forms would be distributed to thousands of incoming students.

Iowa State University Immunization Requirement				
Return this form to: Iowa State University 2260 Thielien Student Health Center Attn: Immunization Clerk Ames, Iowa 50011-2260 Phone: 515-294-9333 Fax: 515-294-3892				
NAME: Last (Family)	First	Middle	Date of Birth	ISU University Identification Number
Permanent Address		City, State, Zip	Permanent Phone Number	
Country of Citizenship	Gender	Iowa State University Entrance Date		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Fall <input type="checkbox"/> Spring <input type="checkbox"/> Summer	Year	
REQUIRED IMMUNIZATIONS OF ALL NEW STUDENTS (including transfer and graduate):				
Proof of immunizations or immunity is required to register for classes				
➔ MEASLES (Rubella) Immunity: Please check one of the four options.				
1. <input type="checkbox"/> I have had two doses of live measles vaccine:				
	First Dose	Must be on or after first birthday <input type="checkbox"/> Measles, Mumps, Rubella <input type="checkbox"/> Measles, Rubella		
	MonthDay	Year		
	Second Dose	Must be given in 1980 or later and at least 30 days after first dose		
	MonthDay	Year		
Signature of Licensed Health Care Provider (OR attach shot record or documentation) Date				
PLEASE DO NOT SEND ORIGINAL DOCUMENTS				
2. <input type="checkbox"/> I have had a Measles (Rubella) titer (blood test) showing immunity (attach a copy of blood test)				
3. <input type="checkbox"/> I have had Measles (Rubella) disease (Health Care Provider documentation of rubella with date of disease attached)				
4. <input type="checkbox"/> I am exempt because I was born before January 1, 1957				
➔ MENINGITIS: Please read the information provided on pages 3 and 4				
1. <input type="checkbox"/> I have been provided information on Meningitis				
2. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I have been vaccinated: <input type="checkbox"/> Menomune (MPSV4) OR <input type="checkbox"/> Menactra (MCV4)				
	Mouth	Day Year		
3. <input type="checkbox"/> No, I have not been vaccinated				
➔ TUBERCULOSIS (TB) Testing is required for all non- U.S. Citizens after arriving in the U.S. This will be done on arrival at ISU.				
RECOMMENDED IMMUNIZATIONS: Please record date of vaccination. See information on back of form.				
Date of last vaccination (month/day/year)				
Mumps:		Rubella:		
Tetanus/diphtheria (Td):		Polio (IPV or OPV):		
Varicella/Chickenpox: Dose #1	Dose #2	or Date of Disease		
Hepatitis A: Dose #1	Dose #2			
Hepatitis B: Dose #1	Dose #2	Dose #3		
Note: If series has NOT been completed, please indicate vaccine used: <input type="checkbox"/> Engenx <input type="checkbox"/> Recombivax				
Tuberculin Skin Test (Mantoux) - *Non-U.S. citizens*; please see instructions on back of form.				
<input type="checkbox"/> Positive <input type="checkbox"/> Negative _____ mm of induration date of test _____				

Immunization Instructions

MEASLES REQUIREMENT
Measles (rubella) is a serious disease that is entirely preventable. Iowa State University follows the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's recommendation for immunization. To prevent the possibility of a measles epidemic occurring here, ISU requires that all new (including transfer and graduate) students show proof of immunization or immunity. If you do not provide this information before September 31st, you will not be allowed to register for the next semester's classes.

Your immunization records can be obtained from your health care provider's office. They may also be available from your high school or from other colleges or universities you have attended. Public health department and military records are also acceptable. Please note that all immunization dates and tests must include the month, day, and year. A photocopy of your immunization record is acceptable and may be attached to this form. **Please do not send original documents.**

IF YOU NEED A MEASLES IMMUNIZATION
The Thielien Student Health Center is located on the northeast corner of Union Drive and Sheldon Avenue, just west of Beyer Hall. New students are eligible for vaccinations and other services beginning with New Student Orientation and throughout the summer. Rubella titers (blood test) and Tuberculosis (TB) skin tests are also available. *TB testing is required of international (non-U.S. citizens) students only and will be part of orientation procedures.* Please note that there will be a charge for the vaccine and tests. You may also visit your current health care provider for a measles vaccination and send the appropriate documentation to the Thielien Student Health Center.

CHECKLIST FOR REQUIREMENTS

- Include two (2) measles immunization dates or proof of immunity
- Read the attached information on meningitis
- Answer the questions on meningitis
- Have your doctor or nurse sign the form OR attach a copy of the immunization form or card. (Many high schools will provide you with this information.) Please do not send your original immunization documents; keep them for your files.

DISEASE AND IMMUNIZATION INFORMATION
Hepatitis A: A viral infection resulting in inflammation of the liver, and often leading to temporary jaundice and flu-like symptoms. May be transmitted by food, sexual contact, or in daycare settings. A two-shot series (the second shot is given 6 months after the first) offers up to 10 years of protection. Advised for all travelers to less developed areas and for homosexual males.
Hepatitis B: A viral infection similar to Hepatitis A but with a risk of developing liver cancer and other complications. Generally transmitted through blood or bodily secretions. A three-shot series is given over 6 months and gives 10 years or more of immunity. Recommended for all students.
Polio: After completion of the childhood series, a booster is recommended only for persons planning to travel to less developed areas.
Tetanus/diphtheria/Pertussis: After the initial childhood series, a booster is recommended every 10 years (5 years for those who travel abroad).
Pneumococcal pneumonia: A one-shot vaccination is advised for students with chronic respiratory, heart, or liver conditions, those with sickle cell disease, those over age 65, and those who have had their spleen removed or have compromised immune systems.
Varicella/Chickenpox: A two-shot series is recommended for those who have not had chickenpox.
Influenza: A one-shot vaccine given each year in the fall. Recommended for all students.

WHAT DO I DO WITH THIS FORM?
After completing this form, mail, fax, or deliver to the Iowa State University Thielien Student Health Center. You may bring the form to orientation and a representative from the Thielien Student Health Center will be there to collect it. **Non-U.S. citizens should bring this form to orientation.** If you have any questions about Iowa State University's immunization requirement, please call (515) 294-9535.

Please keep a copy of this form for your files. Revised 2/06

Figure 1. Initial two pages of original Immunization Requirement form

ANALYSIS

This study set out to examine the components of the redesigned immunization form: the design (or look), the content, and its task structure. In the initial study (Bruski, 2007) of the original form, this is described by Caroline Jarrett as a three-layer form model for examining the design of documents (Lipton, 2007). It was hoped that the redesigned immunization form would fix potential problems identified in the earlier study. These improvements were analyzed using the same qualitative methods, and utilizing the reiterative design process, thus continually refining the immunization form as problems and improvements are identified.

In addition, a random sample of 102 of the redesigned forms was reviewed for this study to examine potential common problems and errors, and to compare where possible, the new design with the prior study which had examined 89 of the original forms (Figure 1).

LOOK

The Immunization Requirement form consisted of four pages, pages one and two were created by the student health center, while pages three and four were from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and were determined to be used "as is" by the health center. The first page had a number of fields that must be written into and boxes than must be checked. Page two contains primarily instructions for the first page, a checklist and also information regarding the various immunizations.

The page layout and use of typography was very inconsistent in the original form (Figure 1). Identified problems (Author, 2007) included lack of grid, inconsistent use of white space (which gives the user spatial cues), and inconsistent use of typographic styles. Formally this left the original design with a cluttered overall appearance. Together this may have accounted for a number of the errors users encounter in filling the form out properly. The subsequent two pages, being from a CDC document, follow a completely different style altogether.

Immunization Requirement

Return this completed form to:
Iowa State University
2250 Thielien Student Health Center
Attn: Immunization Clerk
Ames, Iowa 50011-2250
Phone: 515-294-9535 Fax: 515-294-5892

IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY
Thielien Student Health Center

Last Name (Family) First Middle Date of Birth (Month/Day/Year)

Permanent Address City State Zip

Permanent Phone Number Country of Citizenship ISU Identification Number

Gender: Male Female ISU Entrance Date: Fall Spring Summer Year

ABOUT THE MEASLES REQUIREMENT: Measles (rubeola) is a serious disease that is entirely preventable. Iowa State University follows the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's recommendation for immunization. To prevent the possibility of a measles epidemic occurring here, ISU requires that all new (including transfer and graduate) students show proof of immunization or immunity. If you do not provide this information before September 31st, you will not be allowed to register for the next semester's classes.

Your immunization records can be obtained from your health care provider's office. They may also be available from your high school or from other colleges or universities you have attended. Public health department and military records are also acceptable. Please note that all immunization dates and tests must include the month, day, and year. A photocopy of your immunization record is acceptable and may be attached to this form. *Please do not send original documents.*

IF YOU NEED A MEASLES IMMUNIZATION: The Thielien Student Health Center is located on the northeast corner of Union Drive and Sheldon Avenue, just west of Beyer Hall. New students are eligible for vaccinations and other services beginning with New Student Orientation and throughout the summer. Rubella titers (blood test) and Tuberculosis (TB) skin tests are also available. Please note that there will be a charge for the vaccine and tests. You may also visit your current health care provider for a measles vaccination and send the appropriate documentation to the Thielien Student Health Center.

REQUIRED IMMUNIZATIONS OF ALL NEW STUDENTS (including transfer and graduate)
Proof of immunizations or immunity is required to register for classes.

1. MEASLES (Rubeola) Immunity: Please check one of the four options (A-D)

A. I have had two doses of live measles vaccine:
First Dose Must be on or after first birthday
Month/Day/Year _____
Second Dose Must be given in 1980 or later and at least 30 days after first dose.
Month/Day/Year _____

B. I have had a Measles (Rubella) titer (blood test) showing immunity (attach a copy of blood test)

C. I have had Measles (Rubella) disease (Health Care Provider documentation of rubella with date of disease attached)

D. I am exempt because I was born before January 1, 1957

Attach shot record or documentation! PLEASE DO NOT SEND ORIGINAL DOCUMENTS

OR—

Signature of Licensed Health Care Provider Date (Month/Day/Year) _____

Printed Name of Licensed Health Care Provider Clinic Name Clinic Phone Number _____

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REQUIRED IMMUNIZATION INFORMATION FOR ALL NEW STUDENTS (including transfer and graduate)

2. MENINGITIS (Meningococcal vaccines): Please read the information provided on pages 3 and 4

A. I have been provided information on Meningitis (Meningococcal disease and vaccine)

B. Yes, I have been vaccinated: Menomune (MPSV4) OR Menactra (MCV4) _____
Month Day Year

C. No, I have not been vaccinated

3. REQUIRED IMMUNIZATIONS FOR ALL NON-U.S. Citizens (including transfer and graduate):
TUBERCULOSIS (TB) Screening is required for all non-U.S. Citizens after arriving in the U.S. This will be arranged through the ISU International Office during your orientation.

4. RECOMMENDED IMMUNIZATIONS: Please record date of vaccination and see further information below
Date of last vaccination (month/day/year)

Hepatitis A: Dose #1	Dose #2	Hepatitis B: Dose #1	Dose #2	Dose #3
Note: If series has NOT been completed, please indicate vaccine used: EpiVax/Recombinax				
Influenza	Mumps	Pneumococcal pneumonia:	Polio (IPV or OPV):	
Rubella:	Tetanus/Diphtheria (Td): Varicella/Chickenpox: Dose #1 Dose #2 or Date of Disease			
Tuberculosis Skin Test (Mantoux) - "Non-U.S. citizens", please see instructions on back of form. Positive Negative mm of induration date of test				

HELPFUL DISEASE AND IMMUNIZATION INFORMATION

Hepatitis A: A viral infection resulting in inflammation of the liver, and often leading to temporary jaundice and flu-like symptoms. May be transmitted by food, sexual contact, or in daycare settings. A two-shot series (the second shot is given 6 months after the first) offers up to 10 years of protection. Advised for all travelers to less developed areas and for homosexual males.

Hepatitis B: A viral infection similar to Hepatitis A but with a risk of developing liver cancer and other complications. Generally transmitted through blood or bodily secretions. A three-shot series is given over 6 months and gives 10 years or more of immunity. Recommended for all students.

Influenza: A one-shot vaccine given each year in the fall. Recommended for all students.

Mumps:

Pneumococcal pneumonia: A one-shot vaccination is advised for students with chronic respiratory, heart, or liver conditions, those with sickle cell disease, those over age 65, and those who have had their spleen removed or have compromised immune systems.

Polio: After completion of the childhood series, a booster is recommended only for persons planning to travel to less developed areas.

Rubella:

Tetanus/Diphtheria/Pertussis: After the initial childhood series, a booster is recommended every 10 years (5 years for those who travel abroad).

Tuberculosis:

Varicella/Chickenpox: A two-shot series is recommended for those who have not had chickenpox.

WHAT DO I DO WITH THIS FORM?
Checklist for Requirements

Include two (2) measles immunization dates or proof of immunity

Read the attached information on meningitis

Answer the questions on meningitis

Have your doctor or nurse sign the form OR attach a copy of the immunization form or card. (Many high schools will provide you with this information.) Please do not send your original immunization documents; keep them for your files.

Immunization Instructions
After completing this form, mail, fax, or deliver to the Iowa State University Thielien Student Health Center. You may bring the form to orientation and a representative from the Thielien Student Health Center will be there to collect it. Non-U.S. citizens should bring this form to orientation. If you have any questions about Iowa State University's immunization requirement, please call (515) 294-9535. Please keep a copy of this form for your files.

Iowa State University 2250 Thielien Student Health Center
Attn: Immunization Clerk Ames, Iowa 50011-2250
Phone: 515-294-9535 Fax: 515-294-5892

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Revision 01_0308

Figure 2. Initial two pages of the first redesigned form, "Revision 01_0308".

The initial redesigned form "Revision 01_0308" (Figure 2) used a two-column grid in part to establish a stronger sense of structure and open space for content areas, as this was lacking in the original. These spatial cues are crucial in organizing the perception of space (Schrivver, 1997). In addition, the redesign included the name of the university logotype, and utilized the sans serif typeface from the identity system, Univers. Though serif typefaces are often considered more readable in print communications, in part the sans serif typeface was selected for its clarity as nearly a quarter of these forms are faxed.

CONTENT

As stated earlier, technical jargon and medical terminology can create an inadvertent barrier to communication. Though, for this form, the use of scientific and common names for disease and immunization is necessary, so perhaps the best that could be expected is to be concise and consistent in their use. The original form mixes terms such as "measles", "Measles", "measles (rubeola)", and "measles, mumps, rubella" for example, but never uses the more common term "MMR" (Bruski, 2007). The revised designs (Figures 2, 3, 5) use consistent terminology throughout, for example always referring to measles as "Measles (Rubeola)".

Another issue with the original design was potential confusion regarding the use of headings, stating some immunizations as being required, when that was only true for incoming international students. (Bruski, 2007). Moving them to the appropriate pages then modified these headings.

IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY
Thielen Student Health Center

Immunization Requirement

Return this completed form to:
Iowa State University
2380 Thielen Student Health Center
Attn: Immunization Clerk
Ames, Iowa 50011-2290
Phone: 515-294-9218 Fax: 515-296-6677

Last Name (Family) _____ First _____ Middle _____ Date of Birth (Month/Day/Year) _____

Permanent Address _____ City _____ State _____ Zip _____

Permanent Phone Number _____ Country of Citizenship _____ ISU Identification Number (Middle 9 Digits) _____

Gender: Male Female ISU Entrance Date: Fall Spring Summer Year _____

ABOUT THE MEASLES REQUIREMENT: Measles (rubeola) is a serious disease that is entirely preventable. Iowa State University follows the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's recommendation for immunization. To prevent the possibility of a measles epidemic occurring here, ISU requires that all new (including transfer and graduate) students show proof of immunization or immunity.

ABOUT YOUR RECORDS: Your immunization records can be obtained from your health care provider's office. They may also be available from your high school or from other colleges or universities you have attended. Public health department and military records are also acceptable. Please note that all immunization dates and tests must include the month, day, and year. A photocopy of your immunization record is acceptable and may be attached to this form. *Please do not send original documents.*

REQUIRED IMMUNIZATIONS OF ALL NEW STUDENTS (including transfer and graduate)
Proof of immunizations or immunity is required to register for classes

1. MEASLES (Rubeola) IMMUNITY: Please check one of the five options (A-E)

A. I have had two doses of live measles vaccine:
First Dose Must be on or after first birthday _____
Month/Day/Year _____

Second Dose Must be given in 1800 or later and at least 30 days after first dose. _____
Month/Day/Year _____

B. I have had a Measles (Rubeola) titer (blood test showing immunity [attach a copy of blood test].

C. I have had Measles (Rubeola) disease (Health Care Provider documentation of rubella with date of disease attached).

D. I am exempt because I was born before January 1, 1957.

E. I have a Medical or Religious Exemption (Please attach exemption documentation available from the Iowa Department of Public Health located at http://www.idph.state.ia.us/ADPH/COMMON/pdf/immunization/products/cert_of_immunization.pdf)

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Last Name (Family) _____ First _____ Middle _____ ISU Identification Number (Middle 9 Digits) _____

2. MENINGITIS (Meningococcal vaccines): Please read the information provided on pages 3 and 4

A. I have been provided information on Meningitis (Meningococcal disease and vaccines).

B. Yes, I have been vaccinated: Menomune (MPSV4) OR Menactra (MCV4) _____ (Month/Day/Year)

C. No, I have not been vaccinated.

3. TUBERCULOSIS SCREENING IS REQUIRED FOR ALL NON-U.S. CITIZENS
This will be arranged through the ISU International Office.

RECOMMENDED IMMUNIZATIONS: Please record date of vaccination (Month/Day/Year)

Hepatitis B: Dose #1 _____ Dose #2 _____ Dose #3 _____

Polio (IPV or OPV): Dose #1 _____ Dose #2 _____ Dose #3 _____ Dose #4 _____ Dose #5 _____

Tetanus/Diphtheria (Td): Dose #1 _____ Dose #2 _____ Dose #3 _____ Dose #4 _____ Dose #5 _____

Varicella/Chickenpox: Date of Disease _____ or Dose #1 _____ Dose #2 _____

For Women: Gardasil (HPV): Dose #1 _____ Dose #2 _____

4. ATTACH COPY OF IMMUNIZATION RECORD —or— SIGNATURE FROM HEALTH CARE PROVIDER

(attach a copy of shot record or documentation)

—or—

Signature of Licensed Health Care Provider _____ Date (Month/Day/Year) _____

Printed Name of Licensed Health Care Provider _____ Clinic Name _____ Clinic Phone Number _____

WHAT DO I DO WITH THIS FORM?

Checklist for Requirements

1. Include two (2) measles immunization dates or proof of immunity.

2. Read the attached information on meningitis and answer the questions on meningitis.

3. Contact International Education Office for TB screening.

4. Attach a copy of the immunization record —or— a signature from your health care provider. Many high schools will provide you with this information. Please do not send your original immunization documents; keep them for your files.

Return this form before July 31st.

Immunization Instructions
After completing this form, mail, fax, or deliver to the Iowa State University Thielen Student Health Center. You may bring the form to orientation and a representative from the Thielen Student Health Center will be there to collect it. Non-U.S. citizens should bring this form to orientation. If you have any questions about Iowa State University's immunization requirement, please call (515) 294-9218.

Return this completed form to:
Iowa State University
2380 Thielen Student Health Center
Attn: Immunization Clerk
Ames, Iowa 50011-2290
Phone: 515-294-9218 Fax: 515-296-6677

IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY
Thielen Student Health Center

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Revision 01_0408

Figure 3. Initial two pages of final redesigned form, "Revision 01_0408".

The initial redesigned form (Figure 2) utilized much of the same content as the original, and rearranged it to present a clearer and more consistent appearance. Near the very end of the redesign, only the new definition of "rubella" needed to be inserted, it was discussed between the designer and the student health center that perhaps all of these definitions were not essential, and that more stress should be placed upon receiving full immunization records. This discussion resulted in a second revised design, "Revision 01_0408" (Figure 3) before deployment.

This revision benefited from the elimination of now unnecessary definitions, would have more white space, and could then include an area at the top of page two for the students name and student identity number. This repetition was deemed important, however there was not enough room in the first revision. By repeating this at the information at the top, it would hopefully prevent the pages from becoming separated due to faxing and other factors, as 24% of these redesigned forms were received by the student health center via fax.

TASK STRUCTURE

As previously discussed, the overall content structure of the form was reconfigured. As part of this reconfiguration, more emphasis was placed upon creating a linear task structure, where a user could simply follow the appropriate numbered and lettered steps to complete the form. Where possible, the use of terminology was kept to the appropriate location, whereas the original form had information and terms spread across the two initial pages in an unordered manner (Figure 4). In the prior study of the original form, approximately 1/4 were filled out improperly or not filled out at all (Bruski, 2007). Some of these issues many be attributed to placement of tasks necessary for a user to properly fill out the form and submit it.

Overall, this form has three primary purposes, all of which must be both filled out on the form and documented through the attachment of the immunization record or a signature from a qualified health care provider. The first primary purpose is to document indicated measles immunizations, the second is to disseminate information on meningitis, and the third would be to remind incoming international or non-U.S. citizens to be screened for tuberculosis (TB). A supporting purpose was to document recommended immunizations. As a result, each of these requirements was placed on the document in that order.

The figure displays two pages of a form. The top page is the 'Iowa State University Immunization Requirement' form, which includes fields for personal information, a checklist for immunization requirements, and instructions for parents/guardians. The bottom page is a CDC informational page titled 'MENINGOCOCCAL VACCINES: WHAT YOU NEED TO KNOW'. Red lines and boxes connect specific sections of the form to the CDC page, illustrating a linear task structure. The CDC page includes sections for 'What is meningococcal disease?', 'Who should get meningococcal vaccine and when?', 'What are the risks from meningococcal vaccines?', and 'How many doses?'. The form page includes sections for 'MEASLES REQUIREMENT', 'IF YOU NEED A MEASLES IMMUNIZATION', 'CHECKLIST FOR REQUIREMENTS', 'DISEASE AND IMMUNIZATION INFORMATION', and 'WHAT DO I DO WITH THIS FORM?'.

Figure 4. Task structure of the original Immunization Requirement form (Author, 2007). The bottom two pages from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) were deemed by the health center to be required and should be used “as is”.

REQUIRED IMMUNIZATIONS OF ALL NEW STUDENTS (including transfer and graduate)

Proof of immunizations or immunity is required to register for classes

1. MEASLES (Rubeola) IMMUNITY: Please check one of the five options (A-E)

A. I have had two doses of live measles vaccine:

First Dose *Must be on or after first birthday*

Month/Day/Year

Second Dose *Must be given in 1980 or later and at least 30 days after first dose.*

Month/Day/Year

Measles (Rubeola), Mumps, Rubella (MMR)

Measles (Rubeola), Rubella

Measles (Rubeola)

Measles (Rubeola), Mumps, Rubella (MMR)

Measles (Rubeola), Rubella

Measles (Rubeola)

B. I have had a Measles (Rubeola) titer (blood test) showing immunity [attach a copy of blood test].

C. I have had Measles (Rubeola) disease [Health Care Provider documentation of rubeola with date of disease attached].

D. I am exempt because I was born before January 1, 1957.

E. I have a Medical or Religious Exemption (Please attach exemption documentation available from the Iowa Department of Public Health located at http://www.idph.state.ia.us/ADPER/common/pdf/immunization/products/cert_of_immunization.pdf)

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Figure 5. Steps #1A-E: Final redesigned Immunization Requirement Information Sheet, “Revision 01_0408” (Figure 3), at the bottom of page 1.

Measles immunity task, step #1A-E

Though this task was not tracked in the prior study (Figure 5), in the redesign sample of 102 tracked for this study “Revision 01_0408” (Figure 3):

- 25 filled out this step somewhat incorrectly. In other words, not following the form precisely.

Of that 25:

- 17 did not check #1A, but checked the MMR box to the right and included dates.
- 8 failed to provide any of the necessary information, even somewhat correctly.

In essence, to check #1A and provide dates, or to not check #1A but fill out the dates is essentially an unnecessary redundancy, and means the same thing: I have had two doses of live measles vaccine.

Of those 8 that failed to provide any of the necessary information, even somewhat correctly.:

- 5 were totally blank on the form but attached their immunization record.
- 2 wrote in “see attached” and attached the record.
- 1 that was blank and attached no record.

Essentially, all but one user provided the necessary information the health center requires, just not entered precisely into the immunization form as desired.

For the health center, this requires more work as they cannot reliably just look at the form’s checked boxes, and must look at approximately 25% more closely.

Last Name (Family)

First

Middle

ISU Identification Number (Middle 9 Digits)

2. MENINGITIS (Meningococcal vaccines): Please read the information provided on pages 3 and 4A. I have been provided information on Meningitis (Meningococcal disease and vaccines).B. Yes, I have been vaccinated: Menomune (MPSV4) OR Menactra (MCV4) _____
(Month/Day/Year)C. No, I have not been vaccinated.

Figure 6. Steps #2A-C: Final redesigned Immunization Requirement Information Sheet, "Revision 01_0408" (Figure 3), on the top of page 2.

Meningitis information task, step #2A-C

This step should have two boxes checked (Figure 6), one indicating they had received information regarding the vaccines, and another indicating they have been immunized (plus the date), or checking no, they have not been vaccinated. The original design did not include page numbers, so it was hoped that by numbering the first two pages "Page 1 of 4", and "Page 2 of 4" users may note the CDC document and understand it to be part of the overall packet (Figure 4, bottom). However, 53% did not check the box "I have been provided information on Meningitis", #1A, and on the original form this was 57%. This only slight improvement could be attributed to a couple factors. Firstly, it could be due to the step-by-step nature of the form's redesign, where normally only one lettered box under a numbered heading would need to be checked. Secondly, for the most part, one could infer that whoever is filling out this form would have either been handed the four page form (which includes the two page CDC Meningococcal Vaccine info sheet), downloaded the same four page form as a .pdf file from the student health center, or it would have been mailed to them. It would be logical that most would have received this information unless there was some sort of technical error in the process. Additionally, this issue may also be attributed to the placement of the box near the very top of page two. Simple instructions indicating something similar to "Check two of the appropriate boxes below." may have also helped.

On the original form 34% did not indicate whether they'd been vaccinated or not, and this only improved to 28% on #2 of the revised form. Overall, 7% did not check anything in this step, and 6% only checked #2A (vaccination and date) and not any other box. Interestingly, of the 28% who did not indicate vaccination or not, 55% of them had also not properly filled out the measles immunity task (#1) properly.

Tuberculosis screening task

This task was a reminder step for non-U.S. citizens, or incoming international students, and did not require any sort of documentation on this form.

Immunization documentation task

This step required either an attached copy of the immunization record or the signature and contact information for a licensed health care provider. 68% attached immunization records, and 11% included the signature and contact information. Additionally, for 19% of those that attached the record, the clinic signed and submitted the record though only the record or the signature was needed. Only 2% did not complete this step properly.

Summary of tasks

In reviewing the number of errors, one must consider the most important task of the document: document measles immunizations, disseminate information on meningitis and track immunizations, remind incoming international or non-U.S. citizens to be screened for tuberculosis (TB). For the first task, nearly all the forms contain the proper information, though strictly speaking, the form may not have been properly filled out. The second step saw only marginal improvement in the number of users checking the appropriate box for the reception of the CDC document on pages 3 and 4, and in the number indicating vaccination. There does appear to be a positive correlation between users improperly filling out the first two steps.

Of the secondary tasks, only the “Recommended Immunizations” use can be quantified, and about 85% of the forms filled in at least one of the immunizations, such as chickenpox, polio and hepatitis.

CONTEXT

Though there was a slight decrease in the number of errors once the form was redesigned, lost in all of this was the entire rationale for the forms existence. From the outset, this form and the number of improperly filled out forms the health center was receiving was not necessarily deemed a problem by the center. In fact, the designer heard about the number of errors on the form during the course of a meeting about a different subject altogether, and took the initiative to investigate the matter. Throughout the process of redesign, the designer asked many questions regarding the purpose of the form, what was the primary goal of the form, who used it, and what content needed to be included. In this and other contexts, the designer needs to ask the client questions about the communication intended, and the intended audience. However, to a reasonable extent, the designer must rely upon the expertise of the client in determining certain factors, such as in this case.

The Hodgepodge of Special Cases and Quick Fixes
As stated previously one of the primary purposes of this form is the required distribution of Meningococcal Vaccine Information. Attaching the CDC information to this form does not necessarily mean that someone has actually read it, however the requirement is only to provide this information. Initially it was believed by the health center that this information was required to be distributed in the manner seen in Figure 4, bottom half.

Many processes in health care, much like business do not necessarily come about through design, but by happenstance. One example of how this can happen is provided by Hammer (1990, p. 110) “Why did we design inefficient processes? In a way we didn’t. Many of our procedures were not designed at all; they just happened... Each day brought new challenges and special cases, and the staff adjusted accordingly. The hodgepodge of special cases and quick fixes was passed from one generation of workers to the next.” In this way, forms and processes can inadvertently see a sort of mission creep, whereby the purpose, goals and elements of a design may morph, but no longer address its original purpose.

Such seems to be the case for the meningitis requirement. Nearly a year after implementation of the redesign, all area decision makers met for the first time together with the designer to review the form. During the course of the conversation, it was discovered that it was possible to give a much briefer description of the meningitis requirement given to incoming students, and a web site address would be given for more information in depth. Previous to this, it had just been taken for granted that all information must be provided from the CDC, because, in part, that is how it had been previously done.

	Old Form	New Form
Sample size	89	102
Did not indicate vaccination	34%	28%

Table 1. Only marginal improvement

Figure 7. The variety of immunization records user may encounter from a variety of sources. Clockwise from upper left: a high school in Iowa; China; a school in Iowa; a health clinic in Illinois. Red markings and “EMR” stamps are from the student health clinic indicating the documents contents had been entered into the electronic medical record. Blacked out areas indicate personally identifiable information for the patient, clinic, or health care provider.

A Communication Breakdown

Another major purpose for the forms existence was to document immunizations, particularly required immunizations such as meningitis, measles and TB. As noted in Table 1, despite the design efforts to clean up the design, there was only a 6% improvement in the number of errors. This would amount to hundreds of incoming students having properly filled out forms, which is important, however one fundamental problem all along may have been the complexity of the task being performed. Not only would users have to navigate the previously mentioned vaccination terms, they would also have to decipher myriad versions of immunization records (Figure 7) for which there is no standard form of representation.

As stated by de Stadler and van der Land (2007) “Designing a document from a functional perspective means, among other things, making very clear and concise decisions about the goal(s) of the document and the audience to whom the document will be directed.” In this case, though the form is directed toward someone not part of the medical community, the tasks required are best addressed by members of that community, rather than having someone interpret the information from the immunization record and translate that to the Immunization Requirement Form. As previously noted, 68% of the Forms had Immunization Records attached, which in essence makes some of the other form steps redundant.

<p>IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY Thielen Student Health Center</p>	<p>Immunization Requirement Information Sheet</p>
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1. **ABOUT THE MEASLES REQUIREMENT.** Measles (rubeola) is a serious disease that is entirely preventable. Iowa State University follows the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's recommendation for immunization. To prevent the possibility of a measles epidemic occurring here, ISU requires that all new (including transfer and graduate) students show proof of immunization or immunity. Measles immunizations may be listed on your immunization record as MMR, M/R or Measles. Iowa State University requires proof of 2 immunizations. If you have chosen to provide a positive MMR titer, a record of the lab result must be provided. If you were born prior to January 1, 1957, please call 515-294-9218. If you have a medical or religious exemption please fax a copy of the Iowa Department of Public Health exemption form located at http://www.idph.state.ia.us/ADPER/common/pdf/immunization/products/cert_of_immunization.pdf

ABOUT YOUR RECORDS: Your immunization records can be obtained from your health care provider's office. They may also be available from your high school or from other colleges or universities you have attended. Public health department and military records are also acceptable. Please note that all immunization dates and tests must include the month, day, and year. A photocopy of your immunization record is required and should be attached to this form. *Please do not send original documents.*

IF YOU NEED A MEASLES IMMUNIZATION: The Thielen Student Health Center is located on the northeast corner of Union Drive and Sheldon Avenue, just west of Bayer Hall. Please call 515-294-5801, and use option 1 for an appointment. New students are eligible for vaccinations beginning with New Student Orientation and throughout the summer. Please note that there will be a charge for the vaccines. You may also visit your current health care provider or contact your county health department for a measles vaccination and send the appropriate documentation to the Thielen Student Health Center at 515-296-6677.

INFORMATION IS DUE JULY 31st: If you do not provide this information before July 31st, you may not be allowed to register for the next semester's classes.

2. **TUBERCULOSIS (TB) SCREENING IS REQUIRED FOR INCOMING INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS**
This will be arranged through the ISU International Office, and must be performed after arrival at ISU.

3. **CHECKLIST FOR REQUIREMENTS**

- Obtain a copy of your immunization documentation including 2 measles immunizations.
- Download and complete New Student Health History Form
- Before July 31, fax these forms and immunization documentation to 515-296-6677 or scan and e-mail to tshcmmsr@iastate.edu

Forms may also be mailed to:

Iowa State University
2260 Thielen Student Health Center
Attn: Immunization Clerk
Ames, Iowa 50011-2260
Phone: 515-294-9218 Fax: 515-296-6677
or tshcmmsr@iastate.edu

Page 1 of 1 Revision 02_0309

Figure 8. Final redesigned Immunization Requirement Information Sheet, "Revision 02_0309".

REVISIONS

During the use of the Immunization Requirement form "Revision 01_0408" (Figure 3), periodic revisions were discussed with the health clinic and the designer in the fall of 2008 after the forms had come in for the semester and while the random collection of 102 forms was being analyzed. It was noted that more forms had been received on time, and this was credited in part to the insertion of a due date on the first page and again at the end of a checklist on the second page.

At the beginning of 2009, the health care center and this author met to discuss additions to the form, and other possible modifications to it, such as a brief paragraph or two about meningitis instead of the CDC sheets. During the course of the meeting, the health care providers at the meeting indicated that they preferred having the whole immunization record in addition to the Student Health History Form (an additional item needed at registration time). At this point in time it was noted that a number of other universities were now just requiring submission of only the immunization record with a student's health history, and with just a brief note

about measles. Ultimately it was decided the form was no longer needed, instead it would be replaced with an "Immunization Requirement Information Sheet" (Figure 8).

CONCLUSIONS

It is not uncommon that a pattern of working or process, continues to be utilized well past its ultimate usefulness. We may become sufficiently satisfied with the process to which we've become accustomed, never questioning that it could be improved. Analyzing the document through the lens of look, content and structure was useful in identifying the potential causes of errors for filling out the original immunization form, thus resulting in slight improvements in the redesign. However, engaging in the process of redesigning the form may have led to the most important document improvement of all, the realization that the form was no longer needed.

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